

SURVEY OF ONLINE TEACHING EVALUATION AT SLOVAK UNIVERSITIES DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF TEACHERS

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Abstract

From 2020 to 2022, the COVID-19 pandemic affected many areas of social life, including education. Individual states adopted various safety measures to stop or slow down the spread of the disease based on the recommendations of the World Health Organization, including lockdowns. In this article, we will focus exclusively on the field of higher education in Slovakia during the pandemic, which was implemented in a distance way using various e-learning tools. The transition to distance education was perceived differently among teachers, and it was possible to meet both positive and negative reactions. This article will discuss the survey results of teachers teaching at Slovak universities in more detail. Our goal was to determine how the transition from face-to-face education to distance education was perceived by teachers at Slovak universities during the COVID-19 pandemic and which e-learning tools were used to support the teaching process.

Keywords

COVID-19, distance education, e-learning, higher education, teachers, pandemic

1 Introduction

Many challenges marked the year 2020. Perhaps the biggest challenge was managing the COVID-19 pandemic, which unexpectedly affected the lives of billions of people worldwide. The pandemic has affected many areas of human life, including education. Education was faced with ensuring the continuity of education even when everything seemed uncertain. Due to this problem, a diploma thesis was created at the University of Economics in Bratislava titled *Survey of Online Teaching at Slovak universities during the COVID-19 pandemic*. Ing. Gregor Bilčík wrote this diploma thesis under the guidance of Ing. Pavol Jurík, PhD. Our goal was to survey and determine by what means online teaching was implemented at Slovak universities during the forced transition to distance learning to prevent spreading the disease. As part of the survey, we also focused on the overall evaluation of this type of education compared to traditional face-to-face education (i.e. education in classrooms) from the point of view of teachers and students. Because of this, we implemented two online questionnaire surveys – the first was intended for teachers, and the second one was intended for students. The maximum allowed scope of this article does not allow us to present the results of both surveys. Therefore, in this article, we will

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focus only on the survey conducted with teachers. The student's point of view will be presented in a separate article.

2 State of the art

Online and distance education via the Internet using various e-learning tools formed the foundation for ensuring the educational process during the pandemic. The topic of online teaching and learning has been the subject of several research studies. Martin, Sun, and Westine prepared a systematic review of research on online teaching and learning from 2009 to 2018. In the scientific article, the authors summarise and follow up on previous systematic reviews dating back to 1990. The review showed that in the last decade, the focus of research shifted from instructional characteristics and course design in online education to online engagement and learner characteristics (Martin et al., 2020).

As the study above suggests, online education has existed for a while. However, the arrival of the global pandemic led to its massive spread among students and teachers in Higher education. This has led to the emergence of new studies and surveys similar to ours focused on the field of online teaching in universities during the pandemic. For example, a study from Bangladesh found that university teachers consider online teaching an effective way of teaching during the pandemic. During the pandemic, more than 3/4 of the surveyed respondents preferred online teaching. However, when the question is based on the choice of the preferred method of teaching after the end of the pandemic, a plurality of teachers (45.43%) preferred face-to-face, and slightly fewer teachers (44.52%) preferred a combined (hybrid) mode of teaching. Only 10.05% of teachers in the survey preferred purely online teaching after the end of the pandemic. In the case of e-learning tools to provide online teaching, specifically web-conferencing software, most teachers in Bangladeshi universities used the Zoom platform (Saha et al., 2022). We have different results from a similar survey, but from Europe, which focused on university teachers in Romania. In this survey, the respondents chose MS Teams as the most used web-conferencing software (Barbu et al., 2022).

The use of different software tools and hardware requirements may indicate that such a sudden and massive expansion of online learning was associated with technical problems. The results of a survey of several European university teachers by Schütte et al. confirm their occurrence, but the authors in the scientific article conclude that the problems of online teaching were primarily of a social nature rather than a technical one. This survey showed that teachers lacked direct student interactions (Schütte et al., 2021). This identified drawback of online teaching is in line with the results of a survey from the University of L'Aquila in Italy, where the absence of direct "face-to-face" contact was the main drawback of online teaching considered by teachers (Casacchia et al., 2021).

In Slovakia, studies on online education focus more on students' points of view. Surveys have been conducted among university teachers on this topic, but these were isolated surveys at individual schools or faculties. However, there have been fewer nationwide surveys. In their research, Hvorecký et al. (2021) conducted an online survey in which teachers from Slovak and Czech universities participated. The survey was focused on the transition from on-site face-to-face teaching to fully online teaching. The survey results were analysed as a whole, not separately according to the country they teach. The study showed that most teachers had no previous experience with online teaching, and the sudden transition from face-to-face to online teaching caught them unprepared. However, based on the data, the authors state that university teachers could adapt very quickly to the new mode of education. In addition, Hvorecký et al. found that since the pandemic hit, more teachers had started synchronous online teaching in real-time compared to the period before the lockdowns, which was characterised more by asynchronous online teaching.

Considering the future of online teaching, teachers saw online teaching as only a temporary substitute for face-to-face teaching (Hvorecký et al., 2021).

3 Methodology and goal

The questionnaire survey intended for teachers was carried out from February 19, 2023, to April 3, 2023, and 313 respondents participated. Teachers from 16 Slovak universities were approached (two universities were selected from each region of the Slovak Republic). The number of teachers included in the study in terms of which university they taught at was as follows (Table 1).

Tab. 1: Number of teachers included in the study from different universities

University	Absolute number	Relative number
University of Economics in Bratislava	59	18.85%
Catholic university in Ruzomberok	25	7.99%
University of Prešov in Prešov	19	6.07%
Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra	16	5.11%
Technical University of Zvolen	18	5.75%
Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín in Trenčín	8	2.56%
Trnava University in Trnava	13	4.15%
Comenius University in Bratislava	29	9.27%
Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra	24	7.67%
Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica	20	6.39%
Pavel Jozef Šafárik University in Košice	9	2.88%
University of St. Cyril and Methodius in Trnava	26	8.31%
University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice	14	4.47%
DTI University in Dubnica nad Váhom	4	1.28%
University of Žilina in Žilina	29	9.27%
In total	313	100%

Source: authors

In our survey, we had the largest representation of university teachers from the University of Economics in Bratislava, numbering 59, constituting 18.85% of the entire sample of respondents. The smallest number of respondents were from DTI University in Dubnica nad Váhom, numbering 4, representing 1.28% of all respondents. We also approached teachers from University ISM Slovakia Prešov, but we did not manage to obtain any responses from this school.

Our goal was to find out how the transition from face-to-face education to distance education was perceived by teachers at Slovak universities during the COVID-19 pandemic and which e-learning tools were used to support the teaching process.

The questionnaire for teachers consisted of 11 items, all of which were in the form of questions. There were 10 closed questions and 1 semi-open question in this questionnaire. There were single-choice and multiple-choice questions (the so-called "tick boxes were used") when the respondent could choose more than one answer.

Universities are usually divided into faculties, which are further divided into smaller workplaces (departments, institutes, clinics, etc.). At each faculty, we selected at least one workplace whose teachers we tried to contact. At individual faculties, we prioritised workplaces with the highest number of teaching staff. We have contacted the heads of the selected workplaces, or their secretariats, by e-mail or in person and asked whether we may contact the teachers of the given workplace with a request to fill out our questionnaire. With the leaders' approval, we sent an e-mail message to each teacher of the chosen workplace with information about the survey and a link to the online questionnaire. The teachers' e-mail addresses were publicly available on the official websites of the selected schools or workplaces. In many cases, however, the heads of the workplaces were willing to forward our questionnaire directly to the workplace teachers, or it was forwarded through the secretariat. (it was *the avalanche sampling method*). However, some workplace managers did not respond to our messages.

The avalanche sampling method is based on the principle that one person is contacted, and that person sends the questionnaire to other persons whom the contacted person knows and who fall within the respondent criteria for the given survey. These persons may be able to forward the questionnaire further. The answers are, therefore, "wrapped up" by further sending, and the effect resembles the formation of a snowball.

We also investigated the structure of the respondents in terms of their fields of study. In doing so, we used the classification of study fields, which is presented by "Portál Vysokých Škôl" (which means *Universities Portal* in Slovak language) on its website (Portál VŠ, 2023). This classification and the representation of teachers from the survey in its categories are shown in Figure 1. Most respondents were from the fields of Social, economic, and legal sciences (22.36%). They were followed by Humanities (21.41%), Natural sciences, mathematics, and informatics (16.93%), Healthcare (10.22%), Education (9.58%), Agricultural and veterinary science (7.67%), Security sciences, defence and military (3.19%). The fewest respondents were from the Arts category (1.60%).

Fig. 1: The structure of respondents' fields of study according to the classification of fields of study used by „Portál Vysokých škôl“ (Universities Portal)

Source: Authors

4 Results

At first, we monitored teachers' overall satisfaction with online teaching. The survey showed that 8.63% of teachers were *very satisfied* with online teaching, and 53.99% were *rather satisfied*. Thus, we can conclude that most teachers were satisfied with online teaching. Regarding the negative answers, we found that 32.59% of teachers were *rather dissatisfied*, and 4.79% were *very dissatisfied*. This data can be seen in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Overall satisfaction of teachers with online teaching during the pandemic

Source: Authors

We also evaluated teachers' satisfaction with online teaching according to the categories of taught subjects. The most satisfied teachers in our survey were teachers of *Social, economic, and legal sciences* (60% were rather satisfied, and 11.43% were very satisfied. Thus, 71.43% were satisfied). However, seeing the data we can conclude that satisfaction prevailed in all but one category. The only category where dissatisfaction prevailed was *Security, defence, and military*. In this category, 60% of teachers were dissatisfied, and 40% were satisfied. Interesting is also the result we obtained for teachers who classified their subjects in the category of *Healthcare*. In this category, satisfaction came out exactly 50/50, i.e. 50% of teachers were satisfied (very satisfied or rather satisfied), and 50% were dissatisfied (very dissatisfied or rather dissatisfied). The exact data on teachers' satisfaction with online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic, according to the classification of their subjects into groups of study fields, can be seen in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Teachers' satisfaction with online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic according to the classification of their subjects into groups of study fields

Source: Authors

The level of satisfaction can also be evaluated based on the regions (Figure 4) in which the schools where the respondents teach are located. We noted significant dissatisfaction among the teachers who work in the Košice region, where up to 73.92% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction (thus, they were very dissatisfied or rather dissatisfied) with online teaching during the pandemic. The most satisfied were teachers working in the Trnava region, in which 64.10% of teachers expressed themselves to be rather satisfied and 10.26% were very satisfied in the questionnaire. Thus, we can conclude that 74.36% of teachers in the Trnava region were satisfied with online teaching during the pandemic. The answers in the Prešov region were very similar to the Trnava region. 63.16% of respondents in the Prešov region were rather satisfied, and 10.53% of respondents were very satisfied. Thus, the total satisfaction rate in this region was 73.69%. In the third place in terms of satisfaction was the Bratislava region (69.31% of respondents in this region were very satisfied or rather satisfied).

Fig. 4: Teachers' satisfaction with online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic according to the regions in the Slovak Republic in which they operate/work

Source: Authors

Online education can be conducted in one of three ways:

1. *synchronously* – in an interactive way in real-time (students and the teacher must be online at the same time),
2. *asynchronously* – with a time delay (students and the teacher don't need to be online at the same time),
3. or *as a combination of these two methods* (some activities are done synchronously, while others are done asynchronously).

Our survey found that Slovak university teachers mainly used *synchronous online teaching* (77.64%). This is mainly because the synchronous type of online teaching is the closest to face-to-face teaching. In addition, 20.45% of teachers stated that they *combined elements of both synchronous and asynchronous teaching*. Only 1.92% of teachers exclusively applied the *asynchronous online teaching method* during the pandemic. The preference for synchronous, asynchronous, or combination teaching among the teachers at Slovak universities during the COVID-19 pandemic can be seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: The preference for synchronous, asynchronous, or combination teaching among teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic

Source: Authors

Our survey respondents were also asked to select their primary web-conferencing software during the COVID-19 pandemic. Up to 85.94% of teachers chose *Microsoft Teams*, followed by the *Jitsy Meet* platform (5.75%) and *Google Meet* platform (3.51%). This points to the clear dominance of MS Teams software, which does not necessarily mean it is the best in its category. It is just the most commonly used one. Other systems such as Jitsy Meet, Zoom, Google Meet, BigBlueButton, or Skype were only used in a negligible number of cases. The share of use of individual web conferencing software among teachers at Slovak universities during the COVID-19 pandemic can be seen in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Share of use of individual web-conferencing software among teachers

Source: Authors

MS Teams is a complex system supporting teaching, part of the Microsoft 365 package. It allows real-time transmission of both video and audio (i.e. streaming of lectures and exercises), creation of events representing distance learning hours, viewing and sharing of presentations and other documents with other participants, chatting with participants, writing on a virtual whiteboard, reporting for a word by raising the virtual hands, testing students based on live image and sound transmission (streaming) and other useful functionalities.

Microsoft 365 package (known as Office 365 until April 2020) is a set of cloud services provided by Microsoft on a subscription basis. When it was first introduced in 2011, this package was primarily intended for the corporate sector, but two years later, a variant intended for end users was also launched on the market. It includes applications and services such as Word text editor, Excel spreadsheet, PowerPoint presentation editor, Outlook mail client, OneDrive cloud data storage, OneNote note editor, Teams for Education comprehensive educational support system, and others.

In addition to web-conferencing tools, we tried to find other e-learning tools teachers used to support online teaching during the pandemic. The teachers answered our question: "Which other e-learning tools from the ones listed did you use during online teaching?". It was a closed question, and the respondents could choose one or more options offered in advance. The options offered to the respondents are based on Jurík's classification of e-learning tools (Jurík, 2021). The answers to the above-mentioned question are shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: Various e-learning tools used by teachers during the pandemic

Source: Authors

Among the different options, *the possibility of creating video recordings from online lectures/exercises/seminars* received the most positive answers. 122 teachers created video recordings from teaching units out of a total of 313, which represents 38.98% of teachers from the entire sample. Fewer teachers said they used an *LMS (Learning Management System)* tool (38.02%). According to Simonson, learning management systems are “software systems designed to assist in managing student courses, particularly by assisting instructors and students with course administration. Such systems usually make it possible to track the progress of individual students. They are primarily intended to support distance learning, but are also often used to support face-to-face classroom instruction.” (Simonson, 2007).

Fig. 8: The main benefits of online teaching from the perspective of teachers

Source: Authors

The third most numerous answer to this question were *tools for conducting surveys, surveys, and feedback* (35.78%). This is followed by *tools for better time management* (20.13%), *educational computer games* (12.46%), and *chat applications* (10.86%). Some teachers used *e-portfolios* (5.43%), *podcasts* (4.15%) or they were *writing blogs* (2.9%). No respondent used an *educational social network* (for example, Edmodo falls into this category).

At the same time, it should be noted that 15.02% of teachers told us that they did not use any tool from the possibilities that we offered them.

In the next question, we asked the teachers what they considered the main benefits of online distance teaching. The survey allowed them to choose one or more answers. All benefits arranged in descending order according to their percentage frequency are captured in Figure 8 on the previous page.

We found out that 78.28% of teachers consider online teaching a suitable way to ensure the continuity of teaching in times of crises and unexpected situations. More than half of the teachers also consider the *possibility of easier participation of external lecturers in web conferences* and the *possibility of saving time commuting to work while teaching from home*, among the main benefits of online teaching. On the other hand, *positive effects on mental health* and *increased motivation* were perceived as the main benefits of online teaching only by a low proportion of respondents (less than 5%). 4.47% of teachers think that online teaching has only negatives.

After the question focused on the benefits of online distance teaching, in the next question, we asked the teachers about the main drawbacks of this approach. As in the previous question, in this one, the teachers had pre-prepared options from which they could choose one or more. The results of the answers to the question about the drawbacks of online distance teaching from the teachers' point of view are presented visually in Figure 9.

Fig. 9: The main drawbacks of online teaching from the perspective of teachers

Source: Authors

By far, the most significant drawback of online teaching perceived by teachers was *the lack of direct contact with students and colleagues*, according to 93.29% of respondents. Many teachers also considered students' lower concentration and loss of motivation one of the biggest drawbacks of online teaching (73.16%). Up to 63.26% of teachers also think online teaching provides *more room for students to cheat*.

Given the duration of pandemic restrictions in Slovakia and the various stages of their easing, many teachers had the opportunity to teach online for several semesters. Thus, they can compare individual types of teaching. We tried to find out their preferences in our survey. There are 3 basic types of teaching:

- face-to-face teaching (in a classroom)
- online (distant) teaching
- combined (hybrid) teaching, which combines face-to-face and online teaching – an effective way of implementing a combined form of teaching at universities can be, e.g. conducting lectures in a distance online format and exercises in a face-to-face format directly in the classrooms. Lectures usually do not require practical work from students. They are more about the interpretation of theoretical knowledge, which, in most cases, students can also participate remotely without problems, and it will fulfil the same purpose. It is mainly a one-way transfer of information from the teacher to the students. Exercises, or however, seminars, generally require practical work by students and increased communication with the teacher and each other – if they perform teamwork in groups.

In our survey, we have found out that most teachers (61.98%) prefer face-to-face teaching. This form of teaching is followed by combined (hybrid) teaching (36.10%). Online teaching was preferred only by 1.92% of teachers. These numbers can be seen in Figure 10.

Fig. 10: Teachers' preferred form of teaching

Source: Authors

We also analysed the teachers' preferred form of teaching according to the classification of their subjects into groups of fields of study (Figure 11). Again, we have used the classification of the fields of study which is presented by “Portál Vysokých škôl“ (which means Universities Portal in Slovak language) on its website (Portál VŠ, 2023). We discovered that face-to-face teaching made up more than half of the share in all categories of taught subjects. It was most preferred by teachers from the field of Art (80%). Face-to-face teaching was the least preferred among teachers of Social, economic, and legal sciences (51.43%). We also found that face-to-face teaching was preferred in all Slovak regions. The highest preference was in the Košice region (78.26%), and the lowest in the Bratislava region (50%).

Fig. 11: Teachers' preferred form of teaching according to the classification of their subjects into groups of fields of study

Source: Authors

At the end of the survey, we asked the teachers whether they plan to incorporate some elements of online teaching into face-to-face teaching. 35.14% of respondents stated that they *plan* to incorporate elements of online teaching during in-person classes. About 40.26% of teachers leaned towards the option of *rather yes*. The remaining teachers in the survey chose responses from the negative part of the scale, with 20.45% preferring *rather not* and 4.15% *not*. These results can be seen in Figure 12.

Fig. 12: Teachers' intention to incorporate elements from online teaching also during face-to-face teaching

Source: Authors

5 Conclusion

Among the key findings from the conducted questionnaire survey, we can include the following in particular:

- Most of the teachers who participated in the survey implemented online teaching interactively in real time - they used synchronous online teaching (or also synchronous access). About one-fifth of the teachers combined the synchronous approach with the asynchronous approach.
- The most used web-conferencing tool was Microsoft Teams.
- Teachers often recorded their teaching units in the form of videos and used LMS tools (Learning Management System) and tools for conducting surveys, questionnaires, and obtaining student feedback.
- More than half of the teachers surveyed were either rather satisfied or very satisfied with online teaching. Thus, less than half of the teachers were dissatisfied.
- Online teaching appears to be a suitable way to ensure the continuity of the educational process in times of crises and unexpected situations. This was the most numerous answer regarding the benefits of online teaching (78.27% of respondents said this).
- Most of the teachers in our survey considered the lack of direct contact with students or colleagues as the main drawback of online teaching (93.29%). According to this information, we can conclude that online teaching cannot fully replace real social contact at the moment.
- More than half of teachers prefer face-to-face teaching (61.98%) over distant education.
- 34.14% of teachers plan to apply elements from online teaching also in face-to-face teaching after the experience gained during the pandemic, while 40.26% of teachers said that they rather plan to apply elements from online teaching in face-to-face teaching.

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